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An application of Mask R-CNN in mapping cut slopes using LiDAR digital terrain model

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Abstract

Inventories on cut slopes made for infrastructure development are essential for identifying the locations, dimensions, and formations of man-made slope modifications, serving as a critical resource for hazard assessment and mitigation strategies. Traditionally, such inventories have relied on labor-intensive field surveys and manual interpretation of aerial imagery and contour maps, methods that are both time-consuming and resource-intensive. To address these limitations, this research introduces an automated approach leveraging convolutional neural network (CNN)-based instance segmentation techniques. This study implemented an enhanced CNN model, combining ResNet50 and Mask R-CNN architectures, to extract cut slope topographical features from LiDAR-derived Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and their derivatives, including hill shades, and slope shades. The research focused on the landslide-prone Badulla region in Sri Lanka, spanning 195 km², and incorporated 4,320 cut slope polygons derived through visual interpretation of slope shade raster as ground truth data. To improve model performance, data augmentation techniques were applied to increase the variability of training image tiles. The model achieved an average precision of 0.70 and demonstrated its effectiveness in extracting cut slopes across new spatial extents. Evaluation metrics, including precision, recall, and F1 scores based on feature counts and area-based assessments, consistently exceeded 0.80, confirming the model's accuracy and robustness. Furthermore, deployment in two additional test regions highlighted the model's strong generalization capability when applied to areas with similar LiDAR data properties. The findings underscore the potential of integrating Mask R-CNN with LiDAR for automated mapping and extraction of topographical features, such as cut slopes and landslides. However, there is a need to develop large, standardized topographic training datasets to refine and validate new approaches, paving the way for advancements in automated terrain analysis and hazard mapping.

Keywords: Cut Slopes Mapping, Mask R-CNN, LiDAR DTM, Image Segmentation

1. Introduction

Modifications to slopes in hilly terrains are essential during construction activities, such as highway construction, mining, and urban development. These human-made cut slopes, however, often become sites of slope instability, posing hazards like landslides, rockfalls, cutting failures, and erosion. These hazards can have severe consequences, including damage to infrastructure, environmental degradation, and risks to human lives. Comprehensive cut slope inventories are critical for identifying the location, size, shape, and structural characteristics of these slopes, providing essential data for hazard assessment and mitigation strategies. Such inventories help safeguard social infrastructure and minimize economic losses associated with slope-related hazards [1].

Traditionally, these inventories have been compiled through manual field investigations and aerial image interpretation. While accurate, these methods are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and challenging to scale for large or inaccessible areas. The increasing availability of high-resolution geospatial datasets, such as Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and satellite imagery, offers new opportunities for automated mapping [2]. However, the extraction of meaningful information from these datasets often requires expert interpretation and advanced analytical methods.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning provide a promising alternative. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), known for their strengths in image segmentation and feature extraction, have revolutionised geospatial data analysis. Models like U-Net [3], SegNet [4], and Mask R-CNN [5] have demonstrated their ability to delineate complex topographic features accurately. These models are particularly suited for extracting terrain features like cut slopes because they can process high-resolution spatial data and perform precise pixel-level segmentation.

1.1. Research question and objective

This research aims to address the following questions:

- I. How can CNN-based image segmentation techniques be adapted to accurately extract cut slopes from digital terrain models (DTM)?
- II. What deep learning framework is more suitable for developing a comprehensive cut slope inventory database automating cut slope extraction?

Objectives of this study focus to develop a data-driven framework for extracting cut slopes using advanced CNN models and to create a comprehensive and automated cut slope inventory database.

1.2. Literature review

1.2.1. Traditional methods for slope mapping

Traditionally, slope inventories have been created using manual techniques, including field investigations and aerial photo interpretation. These methods involve mapping slope boundaries and analyzing their stability using empirical models and GIS-based approaches

[1]. While these methods provide valuable data, they are limited by their reliance on labour-intensive workflows and their inability to scale to large regions. Furthermore, manual methods are subject to human error, especially in complex terrain conditions [1].

1.2.2. Advancements in remote sensing and terrain analysis

The development of high-resolution remote sensing technologies, including LiDAR and satellite imagery, has improved the ability to capture detailed topographic features. LiDAR-derived DTMs, in particular, are widely used for landslide detection, slope stability analysis, and terrain mapping [1]. However, the interpretation of these datasets often relies on manual analysis or simple machine learning techniques, which may lack the precision and scalability needed for large-scale slope mapping.

1.2.3. Deep learning algorithms in image segmentation

Deep learning algorithms, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have become transformative tools in geospatial analysis. These models excel in image segmentation tasks, where they classify each pixel in an image to delineate specific features. Among the many CNN architectures, U-Net [3], SegNet [4], and Mask R-CNN [5] have demonstrated remarkable success in tasks requiring high spatial resolution and feature extraction.

- U-Net: Known for its encoder-decoder architecture, U-Net incorporates skip connections to preserve spatial detail during the segmentation process. It has been widely applied in tasks like medical image analysis and land cover classification.
- SegNet: SegNet focuses on efficient pixel-wise classification using an encoder-decoder framework, making it suitable for geospatial tasks like terrain segmentation.

Mask R-CNN, introduced by [5] is an extension of Faster R-CNN that adds a segmentation branch to generate pixel-level masks for each detected object. This model is particularly effective for tasks requiring instance segmentation, where individual objects are segmented and classified separately. Mask R-CNN uses a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to generate regions of interest (RoIs) and applies convolutional filters to these RoIs, enabling precise object detection and segmentation. The versatility of Mask R-CNN has made it a popular choice for geospatial applications. For example:

- Landslide Detection: Mask R-CNN is used to map landslide-prone areas by analysing terrain features in high-resolution DTMs and satellite imagery [6]
- Mining Topographical Features: Mask R-CNN has also been applied to map Mining-Related Valley Fills using LiDAR Digital Elevation Data [7]
- Floodplain Mapping: Mask R-CNN has shown potential for mapping floodplains by integrating terrain data with hydrological models [8]

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

This study focuses on extracting the cut slopes that were developed mainly for housing construction purposes. We applied Mask R-CNN to spot the features of cut slopes from derivatives of digital terrain data. The training area encompasses 181 km² and is mainly located within Badulla District of Sri Lanka. Geographical extents contiguous to the training region, surveyed with the same LiDAR sensor and located within the Badulla district, were included to evaluate model performance throughout the training phase (Testing Area) and to authenticate the final model upon completion (Validation Area).

Figure 1: Study Area with Training, Testing and Validation Regions

To evaluate the model's generalization to new LiDAR-derived topography data, we conducted supplementary validations in two regions of Kegalle (143 km²) and Nuwaraeliya (111 km²). Overall, the model was trained on a single large area, tested on a smaller area that is adjacent to it (14 km²), and then used to make predictions in a new area that was acquired using the same LiDAR DTM data with a spatial resolution of 2 meters, as well as in two other areas that were mapped using the same LiDAR data and were in different districts. Figure 1 shows the study area and extent of training, testing, and validation regions.

2.2. Methodology

This research proposes a deep learning-based (Mask R-CNN) approach for identifying cut slopes in complex landscapes using LiDAR DTM as a key input. The methodology involves preparing different DTM-derived features, generating image chips with various augmentation techniques, and training a Mask R-CNN model with a ResNet-50 backbone. The model's performance is evaluated using statistical measures like intersection over union and mean average precision, and visual assessment is conducted to compare the differences between actual and predicted features and suitability of the model. This approach offers a robust and accurate solution for automated cut slope identification, aiding in various applications such as slope failure risk assessment. Figure 2 refers the overall methodology.

Figure 2: Research Methodology

2.3. Input Data Collection and Pre-Processing

The airborne LiDAR data utilized in this study were acquired as classified point clouds from the Survey Department of Sri Lanka. The density of classified ground point is 1 point per square meter (ppsm) and was surveyed in 2016, achieving a vertical accuracy of 30 cm. Point clouds were transformed into raster data to generate a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) utilizing only the points designated as ground returns and the LAS Dataset to Raster tool in ArcGIS Pro 3(ESRI, 2024). The mean ground elevation was computed for each cell, and linear interpolation was employed to address data gaps. We gridded the raster data to a 2 m spatial resolution considering the significant visibility of cut slopes and associated topographic features at this scale.

To characterize the topographic features of cut slopes, various visualization techniques were applied to the Digital Terrain Model (DTM). These included the use of hillshades with varying azimuths and altitudes, curvatures, and inverted slope maps to emphasize the cut slopes. However, hillshades were excluded from the final analysis due

to their inconsistent representations of terrain, which depended on the sun's angle of elevation and relative position. While curvature rasters statistically depicted the shape of the terrain, they were unable to display the size of the cut slopes or distinguish them from other similar terrain features. Among the tested methods, the slopeshade derived from the slope raster provided a more distinct and interpretable representation of cut slopes, which was further validated using pre-modelling with the Mask R-CNN model.

The slope raster, created using the Slope Tool in ArcGIS Pro 3.3 (Spatial Analyst), was visualized with an inverted grayscale colour ramp to produce the slopeshade raster. In this representation, darker shades indicate steeper slopes, while brighter shades correspond to flatter areas [9]. Figure 3 shows the visual representation of the cut slopes through the slopeshade. To facilitate the generation of training chips and enable its use in the Mask R-CNN model, the slopeshade raster was transformed into an 8-bit integer format by applying the following equation proposed by Maxwell, A.E., et al. (Maxwell et al., 2020).

$$\text{Slopeshade} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Slope}}{90}\right) \times 255$$

Figure 3: Grayscale Slopeshade Imagery representing the cut slopes

2.4. Generating the image chips for training the model

To provide training and testing data for the Mask R-CNN algorithm, the geographic extents were divided into 128-by-128-pixel image chips using the Export Training Data for Deep Learning Tool in ArcGIS Pro 3.3. The filter size was determined by the average size of the cut slope features and the surrounding topography, to enhance the number of training data, a stride of 64 pixels was applied in both the X- and Y-directions to create overlap. To reduce overfitting, data augmentation techniques were employed to enhance the diversity of training features with varying characteristics [10]. The first approach involved rotating the image tiles at multiple angles (45°, 90°, 135°, 180°, 225°, 270°, 315°, and 360°). Additionally, the Focal Statistics tool in ArcGIS Pro was utilized to introduce variations by applying blurring and sharpening effects without changing pixel size. This process generated 28,800 training chips and 4,760 testing chips, each containing at least one feature of the cut slopes and an average of 6 features as shown in Table 1. For each image chip, training masks were also created, where non-cut slope pixels were coded as 0, and each cut slope feature was assigned a unique value, ranging from 1 to the total number of cut slope features in the extent, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 1: Training Data Statistics

```
images = 28800 *3*128*128
Class feature statistics:
features = 161692
features per image = [min = 1, mean = 5.61, max = 37]
classes = 1
cls name          cls value  images  features  min size  mean size  max size
1                  1         28800   161692    0.00     450.36    24032.75
```


Figure 4: Image 1 shows the image chip (128 X 128) and relevant training mask with 8 mapped cut slopes shown by image 2 and the value 0 indicate the background

2.5. Applying Mask R-CNN algorithm for model training

Model training is implemented using the deep learning packages (Python 3, Keras, and Tensorflow), Geoprocessing tools (Export Training Data for Deep Learning and Detect Objects Using Deep Learning) and Notebook environment in Arc GIS Pro 3.3. Initially, model learning proceeded for 20 epochs with the optimal learning rate extracted from the learning curve during the training process. It has been noticed that the model stabilized at 15 epochs, and the optimal learning rate of 0.00015 was used for all epochs (forward and backward through neural networks). the default properties were kept for the additional model arguments for object detection, this includes RPN anchor scales and ratios, backbone strides of the feature pyramid network (FPN), and RoI positive ratio. To facilitate the transfer learning approach, the ResNet50 backbone model was selected, this residual network trained on the Imagenet Dataset that contains more than 1 million images and is 50 layers deep [11]. During each epoch, 3,600 training steps and 595 validation steps were conducted, with a batch size of three image chips. This setup allowed the use of 28,800 training samples and 4760 test samples per epoch. The final model was selected based on the one that achieved the lowest loss value when predicting the test samples.

2.6. Model Testing and Post-Processing the outputs

The Mask R-CNN based model (in the format of Esri model definition JSON file (.emd)) with the precision score of 0.706 derived through the interactive training steps was utilized to detect the cut slopes in the validation area adjacent to training region and in the Kegalle and Nuwereliya districts. This task was done using the Detect Objects Using Deep Learning tool, the 8-bit slopeshade raster of the validation area was used as input image to detect objects, and output is defined as a polygon feature class that contain cut slope geometries.

The model arguments are derived from the trained model definition file. Padding was configured to 32 pixels to minimize edge artefacts and ensure smoother feature representation when merging predictions from adjacent image tiles. A confidence threshold of 0.7 was applied, allowing only predictions with confidence scores exceeding this value to be included in the results. The tile size was set to 128 pixels, consistent with the size used for the training image chips. Additionally, non-maximum suppression was utilized to eliminate duplicate boundaries representing the same cut slope feature class, prioritizing the prediction with the highest confidence score as defined in the model arguments.

2.7. Accuracy Assessment

To evaluate the performance and accuracy of the cut slope image segmentation algorithm, the Mean Average Precision (mAP) metric was calculated using key parameters such as Intersection over Union (IoU), Precision, and Recall. The IoU metric, as defined by Henderson et al., (2017), measures the degree of overlap between predicted cut slope feature classes and manually digitized cut slope polygons, using the equation:

$$IoU = \frac{A_p \cap A_g}{A_p \cup A_g}$$

where (A_p) represents the predicted features, and (A_g) denotes the ground-truth masks. Since the final prediction output consists of polygon vectors over a continuous geographic extent, overlapping image chips can result in multiple evaluations of the same cut slope feature. This approach does not accurately reflect the final prediction's performance. Therefore, the evaluation focuses on demarcating cut slopes as distinct spatial instances across the dataset. Key measures for this assessment include true positives (TP), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) [12]. A predicted feature was classified as a TP if it significantly overlapped with a manually digitized cut slope in terms of shared area and shape. FPs referred to areas incorrectly mapped as cut slopes, while FNs represented non cut slopes in the ground predicted as no cut slope. Feature counts for these measures were derived using the Compute Accuracy for Object Detection Tool in ArcGIS Pro 3.0.

Precision, Recall, and the F1 Score were used to summarize performance:

$$Precision (P) = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad Recall (R) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad F1\ Score = 2 \times \frac{Recall \times Precision}{Recall + Precision}$$

The Average Precision (AP) metric measures the precision averaged across all recall values from 0 to 1 for a given IoU threshold. AP is approximated using discrete recall points as follows: $AP = \sum [R_{n+1} - R_n] \cdot P(R_n)$, where R_n and $P(R_n)$ represent recall and precision at each step. Finally, the mAP is calculated as the mean of AP values across all N categories:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i$$

This approach provides a comprehensive evaluation of the model's ability to delineate cut slope features accurately.

3. Results

3.1. Model's accuracy

Figure 5 illustrates the loss curve, which monitors the errors of the Mask R-CNN model throughout training and validation over 20 epochs. The training and validation losses consistently decline, signifying efficient learning and reduction of errors. At epoch 19, the training loss is 0.9486 and the validation loss is 0.9687, indicating effective model generalization without overfitting. The substantial decrease in loss during the initial epochs indicates rapid weight modifications, although slight variations at particular epochs imply effective training. The minimal disparity of 0.02 between training and validation loss at the end validates the model's reliable performance. The trends suggest effective training; nevertheless, slight adjustments could enhance performance further.

Figure 5: loss curve for Training and Validation

Accuracy measures were generated for testing and validation area with different IOU threshold values as suggested by the [7] to evaluate how model's prediction match with manually digitized cut slope boundaries in different geographical extent, following figure 6 visualize how IoU is interpreted based the cut slope features. By considering the fact that cut slope boundaries vary in geometry and the spatial resolution of the input image is 2M, minor overlap differences between inference features and actual boundary data made no significance. First, required measures such as TP, FP, FN are calculated using Compute Accuracy for Object Detection Tool in ArcGIS Pro. Following table 2 shows accuracy measures in terms of different Intersection over Union for testing area.

Figure 6: Representation of IoU based on Cut Slopes

Table 2: Accuracy measures derived in Testing area based on IoU thresholds

Testing Area				
	IoU (60%)	IoU (70%)	IoU (80%)	IoU (90%)
Precision	0.81	0.76	0.68	0.45
Recall	0.76	0.72	0.65	0.43
F1 Score	0.78	0.74	0.66	0.44
AP	0.69	0.64	0.54	0.26
True Positive	1033	980	875	582
False Positive	249	302	407	700
False Negative	320	373	478	771

At lower IoU thresholds (60%-70%), the model achieves high precision (0.81–0.76) and recall (0.76–0.72), indicating effective detection with fewer false positives and negatives. However, as IoU thresholds increase (80%-90%), stricter overlap requirements reduce precision (0.68–0.45), recall (0.65–0.43), and F1-scores (0.66–0.44), while false positives and false negatives rise significantly. The Average Precision (AP) decreases from 0.69 to 0.26, reflecting the model’s difficulty in achieving fine-grained localization under stricter conditions. True positives also decline from 1033 at IoU 60% to 582 at IoU 90%. This generally suggests that with this narrow threshold range for IoU, cut slopes were detected, but the boundaries did not match well due to the indeterminate and complex nature of the cut slopes and spatial resolution, as discussed. Further optimization could improve performance for stricter IoU criteria. This indicates that within this narrow IoU threshold range, the model successfully detected cut slopes, but the boundary alignment was inconsistent due to the complex and ambiguous nature of the cut slopes, as well as the limitations in spatial resolution. Enhancing the model through further optimization, such as refining hyperparameters or increasing the spatial resolution of input data, could improve its performance under stricter IoU threshold.

3.2. Visual Assessment

In order to understand the variation between the predicted cut slopes and the digitized data a visual comparison is conducted based on the results from the testing and validation area. the following figure 7 shows the differences in the shape and size of the cut slopes (predicted and ground truth) in a portion of validation area in Kegalle. In general, shapes of the cut slopes are similar in the predicted output by the model and digitized references, however the boundaries of predicted features do not intersect precisely due to their ambiguous nature, as discussed earlier, and this trend is statistically reflected by lower precision and recall values when IoU ratio increased.

Figure 7: Comparison of Cut slopes derived from manual digitisation and prediction

The model demonstrates limited effectiveness in predicting comparatively small cut slope features, with boundary edges appearing less refined compared to the training data. This can be attributed to the pixel size of the input raster used during prediction. In cases where adjacent cut slopes are located in close proximity, they are often merged and represented as a single feature in the predictions. Additionally, the model occasionally underrepresents the filled areas of cut slopes, predicting only a smaller portion of the filled regions, even when these regions are substantially larger than the actual cut slope areas.

4. Discussion

Results derived from the cut slopes model, indicate that Mask R-CNN is capable in extract terrain features from DTM if the features have a unique topographic signature. Count-based precision, recall, and F1 scores were all above 0.80 across all validation datasets. Assessment based on similarity of area using different Intersection over Union threshold range gives lower associated recall and precision values. This highlights the difficulty in plotting and evaluating boundaries that are poorly defined or vary in scale. Visual interpretation suggests that the features were generally successfully mapped, though

the borders may be dissimilar. Prediction made by the model in different geographical extents of validation region (Kegalle and Nuwereliya) shows the similar results as in the training area and suggest as long as the input data's (LiDAR DTM) properties are same, the model can be applied to regional mapping. Overall, this research study shows potential in applying instance image segmentation to digital terrain data, suggesting that CNN-based deep learning has potential for mapping other topographic features, for instance past landslides and landslide geomorphologies. This study establishes that the Mask R-CNN deep learning model is well-suited for extracting topographic features characterized by distinctive spatial, contextual, or textural patterns, even when these features are not spectrally distinguishable from surrounding background classes.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of a Mask R-CNN-based instance image segmentation approach for mapping cut slopes associated with housing development using high-resolution LiDAR-derived DTMs. The results highlight the model's ability to effectively extract specific topographic features when trained on a comprehensive and diverse dataset. The well-trained model showed strong transferability, successfully making predictions across spatial extents with input data characteristics similar to those used during training. This underscores the broader applicability of the approach to regional mapping tasks. As this research focused on cut slope features with distinct spatial and geomorphic characteristics, providing a solid foundation for future research. However, further investigation is recommended to map additional topographic features associated with varying types of cut slopes. To improve the model's capacity for accurately delineating complex and ambiguous boundaries, future work should explore advanced optimization techniques and standardized post-processing methods. These enhancements could refine the precision and robustness of terrain feature extraction for diverse applications.

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References

- [1] S. Lee and J. Choi, "Landslide susceptibility mapping using GIS and the weight-of-evidence model," *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 789-814, 2004.
- [2] G. Lin, A. Milan, C. Shen, and I. Reid, "RefineNet: Multi-path refinement networks for high-resolution semantic segmentation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2017, pp. 1925-1934.
- [3] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention (MICCAI)*, 2015, pp. 234-241.
- [4] V. Badrinarayanan, A. Kendall, and R. Cipolla, "SegNet: A deep convolutional encoder-decoder architecture for image segmentation," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 2481-2495, 2017.
- [5] K. He, G. Gkioxari, P. Dollár, and R. Girshick, "Mask R-CNN," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2017, pp. 2961-2969.
- [6] O. Ghorbanzadeh et al., "Landslide detection using deep learning convolution neural networks," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 221, pp. 180-192, 2019.
- [7] Maxwell, A. E., Pourmohammadi, P., & Poyner, J. D. (2020). Mapping the topographic features of mining-related valley fills using mask R-CNN deep learning and digital elevation data. *Remote Sensing*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030547>
- [8] Z. Chen, Y. Zhang, and X. Jiang, "Application of deep learning in automated road segmentation," *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, vol. 18, p. 100298, 2020.
- [9] Haneberg, W. C., Cole, W. F., & Kasali, G. (2009). High-resolution lidar-based landslide hazard mapping and modeling, UCSF Parnassus Campus, San Francisco, USA. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 68(2), 263–276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10064-009-0204-3>
- [10] Zhu, X. X., Tuia, D., Mou, L., Xia, G.-S., Zhang, L., Xu, F., & Fraundorfer, F. (2017). Deep Learning in Remote Sensing: A Comprehensive Review and List of Resources. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, 5(4), 8–36. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2017.2762307>
- [11] He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (n.d.). Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. <http://image-net.org/challenges/LSVRC/2015/>
- [12] Goutte, C., & Gaussier, E. (2005). A Probabilistic Interpretation of Precision, Recall and F-Score, with Implication for Evaluation. In D. E. Losada & J. M. Fernández-Luna (Eds.), *Advances in Information Retrieval* (pp. 345–359). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [13] Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 25, pp. 1097-1105, 2012.
- [14] J. Long, E. Shelhamer, and T. Darrell, "Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2015, pp. 3431-3440.
- [15] L. C. Chen, G. Papandreou, I. Kokkinos, K. Murphy, and A. L. Yuille, "Deeplab: Semantic image segmentation with deep convolutional nets, atrous convolution, and fully connected CRFs," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 834-848, 2018.
- [16] H. Zhao, J. Shi, X. Qi, X. Wang, and J. Jia, "Pyramid scene parsing network," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2017, pp. 2881-2890.
- [17] S. Zheng, S. Jayasumana, B. Romera-Paredes, et al., "Conditional random fields as recurrent neural networks," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2015, pp. 1529-1537.

- [18] G. Huang, Z. Liu, L. Van Der Maaten, and K. Q. Weinberger, "Densely connected convolutional networks," in Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2017, pp. 4700-4708.
- [19] K. Sun, B. Xiao, D. Liu, and J. Wang, "High-resolution representations for labeling pixels and regions," in Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision, 2019, pp. 1735-1744.
- [20] ESRI. (2024). LAS Dataset To Raster (Conversion). ArcGIS Pro 3.4